

Palladium(II), Copper(II) and Nickel(II) Complexes of Arylazo-Bis-Acetoximes

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Phenylazo-bis-acetoxime(PABA), *p*-chlorophenylazo-bis-acetoxime (*p*-CPABA), *p*-anisylazo-bis-acetoxime (*p*-AABA) and *p*-tolylazo-bis-acetoxime (*p*-TABA) react with Pd(II), Cu(II) and Ni(II) to give insoluble complexes with 1 : 2 metal-ligand composition. The electronic spectral, magnetic, I. R. and thermal studies of the complexes were made.

In our earlier communication¹ we have studied phenylazo-*bis*-benzaloxime as gravimetric reagent for Pd(II), Cu(II) and Ni(II). In the present communication, phenylazo-*bis*-acetoxime, *p*-chlorophenylazo-*bis*-acetoxime, *p*-anisylazo-*bis*-acetoxime and *p*-tolylazo-*bis*-acetoxime are reported as new gravimetric reagents for palladium(II), copper(II) and nickel(II). Palladium(II) and copper(II) are quantitatively precipitated at pH 3.0-6.5 and 3.5-7.0 respectively while nickel(II) at 7.0-8.0 with *p*-chlorophenylazo-*bis*-acetoxime and at 8.0-10.0 with other ligands. Pd(II), Cu(II) and Ni(II) are separated from a large number of cations and anions with these reagents similar to phenylazo-*bis*-benzaloxime¹.

Experimental

Standard solutions of Cu(II), and Ni(II) were prepared by dissolving A.R. (B.D.H.) copper sulphate and nickel ammonium sulphate respectively in distilled water and that of Pd(II) by dissolving palladium chloride in conc. HCl (A.R.), diluting and estimating its palladium content with dimethylglyoxime. 1% solutions of foreign ions were prepared by dissolving their nitrates or acetates in distilled water.

The reagents, arylazo-*bis*-acetoximes, were prepared by coupling corresponding diazonium chloride (1 mole) with acetoxime (2 mole) in dilute sodium hydroxide solution keeping pH ~ 10 and temperature 0°. The products were crystallized from alcohol-water mixture as cream coloured crystalline compounds. The properties and analytical data of the ligands are recorded in Table 1. 1% solutions of the reagents in 95% alcohol were used in all estimations.

Elico LI 10 pH meter and Phillips PR 9500 conductivity bridge were used for pH and conductivity measurements. Magnetic measurements were carried out on Guoy's Balance and electronic spectral measurements on Bausch and Lomb spectronic '20'. Thermogravimetric studies were made in air on Stanton thermobalance (high temperature model, 1 mg. sensitivity) and DTA curves were scanned using Mettler-TA 20 model in an atmosphere of nitrogen.

Determination of Pd(II), Cu(II) and Ni(II)

The pH of the solutions containing 10-25 mg of the metal were adjusted in between 5.0-5.5 in case of Pd(II) and Cu(II) with the help of 0.1N acetic acid and 5% ammonia and at 7.5-8.5 in case of Ni(II) with the help of N-HCl and 10% ammonia. Precipitation was carried out at room temperature by adding 1% alcoholic solution of the reagent dropwise with constant stirring till it was complete. It was allowed to stand for about an hour, diluted with distilled water (till alc : H₂O ~ 1:3) and again allowed to stand for an hour at room temperature. The complex was filtered, washed first with distilled water and then with 40% alcohol and dried to a constant weight at 115-120°. The results were found to be within ±0.5% error both in the presence or absence of foreign ions.

Results and Discussion

Properties of the Complexes : The properties and analytical data of Pd(II), Cu(II) and Ni(II) complexes with the reagents are recorded in Table 1. They are soluble in dioxan, acetone, chloroform, benzene, carbon tetrachloride and practically insoluble in alcohol and petroleum ether. They are crystallized from acetone-water mixture. The molecular weight of the complexes, determined by cryoscopic method (Rast's Camphor method), was in agreement with the empirical formula weight showing their monomeric nature.

Conductometric and pH metric titrations indicated 1:2 metal-ligand ratio in all the complexes.

Stability of the Complexes : The stability of the complexes was determined spectrophotometrically by mole-ratio method. A constant volume of the cation solution was titrated against equimolar solution of the reagents at suitable wave-lengths keeping the total volume constant in each case. The absorbance was measured for each successive addition of the reagent. The stability constants and free energy values for the different complexes are recorded in Table 2.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA OF ARYLAZO-BIS-OXIMES AND THEIR Pd(II), Cu(II) AND Ni(II) COMPLEXES

Name	Colour	m. p. °C	Elemental analysis %				Magnetic moment B. M.	I. R. cm ⁻¹			
			Cal Metal	N	Found Metal	N					
PABA	Cream	140	—	22.40	—	22.32	—	3180	1425	1380	1365
(PABA) ₂ Pd	Dark brown	148	17.55	18.54	17.62	18.46	Diamagnetic	—	1410	1380	1365
(PABA) ₂ Cu	Chocolate brown	175	11.30	19.94	11.24	20.00	1.78	—	1415	1380	1365
(PABA) ₂ Ni	Bright Yellow	168	10.54	20.11	10.46	20.18	Diamagnetic	—	1415	1380	1365
<i>p</i> -CPABA	Cream	123	—	19.68	—	19.72	—	3160	1425	1380	1365
(<i>p</i> -CPABA) ₂ Pd	Dark brown	142	15.81	16.64	15.90	16.55	Diamagnetic	—	1410	1375	1360
(<i>p</i> -CPABA) ₂ Cu	Brown	174	10.07	17.76	10.03	17.82	1.80	—	1415	1380	1365
(<i>p</i> -CPABA) ₂ Ni	Bright Yellow	157	9.35	17.90	9.42	17.95	Diamagnetic	—	1415	1380	1365
<i>p</i> -TABA	Cream	141	—	21.21	—	21.16	—	3160	1425	1380	1365
(<i>p</i> -TABA) ₂ Pd	Dark brown	157	16.76	17.71	16.70	17.80	Diamagnetic	—	1415	1370	1360
(<i>p</i> -TABA) ₂ Cu	Yellowish red	174	10.77	18.99	10.72	18.88	1.78	—	1420	1375	1360
(<i>p</i> -TABA) ₂ Ni	Yellow	194	10.23	19.15	10.30	19.20	Diamagnetic	—	1420	1380	1365
<i>p</i> -AABA	Cream	130	—	20.00	—	20.05	—	3180	1430	1380	1365
(<i>p</i> -AABA) ₂ Pd	Dark brown	149	15.96	16.86	15.86	16.78	Diamagnetic	—	1415	1380	1360
(<i>p</i> -AABA) ₂ Cu	Buff	177	10.21	18.02	10.15	18.10	1.80	—	1420	1375	1360
(<i>p</i> -AABA) ₂ Ni	Yellow	167	9.51	18.16	9.46	18.20	Diamagnetic	—	1420	1380	1365

TABLE 2—SPECTROPHOTOMETRIC AND THERMAL ANALYTICAL DATA OF ARYLAZO-BIS-OXIMES AND THEIR Pd(II), Cu(II) AND Ni(II) COMPLEXES.

Name of Compound	Stability Constant log K	Free energy Δ F	Thermal analysis	
			Maximum Wt. loss found %	Maximum loss Cal. for metal oxide formation %
(PABA) ₂ Pd	16.30	-22.60	79.25	79.75
(PABA) ₂ Cu	14.38	-19.94	85.40	85.84
(PABA) ₂ Ni	13.44	-18.63	86.08	86.58
(<i>p</i> -CPABA) ₂ Pd	14.72	-20.41	81.25	81.88
(<i>p</i> -CPABA) ₂ Cu	12.83	-17.78	86.67	87.10
(<i>p</i> -CPABA) ₂ Ni	11.85	-16.43	87.50	88.11
(<i>p</i> -TABA) ₂ Pd	17.18	-23.82	80.20	80.65
(<i>p</i> -TABA) ₂ Cu	15.25	-21.13	86.00	86.52
(<i>p</i> -TABA) ₂ Ni	14.30	-19.83	87.70	87.24
(<i>p</i> -AABA) ₂ Pd	17.77	-24.63	81.16	81.56
(<i>p</i> -AABA) ₂ Cu	15.88	-22.02	86.70	87.20
(<i>p</i> -AABA) ₂ Ni	14.93	-20.70	87.40	87.88

The stability order found is Pd > Cu > Ni which is in accordance with Irving-William Rule. The order of stability constants for the same metal with different substitutions in the phenyl ring of reagent is $(-\text{OCH}_3) > (-\text{CH}_3) > (-\text{H}) > (-\text{Cl})$. The increase in the stability of complexes with methyl group in para position may be explained on the basis of +I effect of the methyl group. It is further increased with methoxy $(-\text{OCH}_3)$ group, which may be attributed to the +M effect of the methoxy group. The complexes with chloro group in the para position are less stable than complexes with no substitution in the phenyl ring probably due to -I effect of chlorine.

Thermal Study : About 25-30 mg of recrystallised and dried complexes were heated in thermogravimetric balance and 10-12mg were taken in DTA. The TGA curves indicated that there is no loss in weight of complexes up to $\sim 185^\circ$. The complexes start to decompose at $\sim 190^\circ$ with a maximum loss at about 450° which corresponds to the formation of metal oxide. The results are recorded in Table 2. These results were also confirmed by endothermic peaks in DTA curves of complexes.

Structure of the Complexes : The results of the infra-red studies of the ligands and their complexes are recorded in Table 1.

The ligands show strong absorption bands in infra-red characteristic of a $(-\text{OH})$ stretching at $3160-3180 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. This band in free $(-\text{OH})$ appears at about 3600 cm^{-1} . Hydrogen bonding, however, shifts this band to lower frequency. This is true because $(-\text{OH})$ group in the reagent molecules is placed in a very close proximity of the polar unsymmetrically substituted azo $(-\text{N}=\text{N}-)$ group. The disappearance of this band in the complexes points to the replacement of hydrogen from $(-\text{OH})$ group by the metal. A strong and sharp band at $\sim 1425 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the molecule of ligands may be assigned to $(-\text{N}=\text{N}-)$ group which is slightly lowered in the complexes. A doublet of two bands at ~ 1380 and 1365 cm^{-1} , which is uniformly observed in infra-red spectra of all the ligands and their complexes, can safely be ascribed to terminal gem dimethyl group. The ligands show two regions of absorption viz $285-295$ and $305-310 \text{ m}\mu$, the former is presumably

the band characteristic of aromatic amines and the latter probably due to conjugation between $-\text{N}=\text{N}-$ system and the aryl nucleus referred to as K-band^{2,3}.

(PdL₂): The diamagnetic Pd(II) complexes are probably square planar which is the common stereochemistry for the palladium complexes.

(CuL₂): These complexes have the magnetic moment of $\sim 1.80 \text{ B. M.}$ which are considerably lower than that of the tetragonally distorted octahedral or a tetrahedral Cu(II) complex⁴. The lower magnetic moment may be a result of increased separation between the ground ${}^2\text{B}_{1g}$ and the components of ${}^2\text{T}_{2g}$ term of the energy level for Cu(II) ion with a square planar symmetry⁵. The broad band at $\sim 560 \text{ m}\mu$ in the visible spectra of the complexes also points to the square planar stereochemistry of the Cu-complexes.

(NiL₂): These complexes were found to be diamagnetic. The electronic spectra of the complexes exhibit two shoulders at $\sim 410 \text{ m}\mu$ and $\sim 510 \text{ m}\mu$ which point to their square planar stereochemistry.

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